
Statistics of Correlated Radioactive Contaminations

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Abstract

The statistical approach to the assessment of radiation doses for members of the public was developed. It considers the fallout correlation for different radionuclides in case of emergency situations at nuclear fuel cycle facilities. A computational procedure based on covariance matrix was formulated for the purpose to calculate the multidimensional function of the distribution of partial radiation doses from contaminating radionuclides. Test calculations have shown that the consideration of the correlation between the contamination components allows avoiding significant mistakes in the statistical evaluation of the total radiation dose.

Keywords: Radiation accidents, distributed radiation dose, standard exceedance probability, correlated contaminations, covariance matrix, lognormal distribution, multivariate distribution function

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Introduction

Improvement of calculating tools (models and program codes) is the necessary precondition for the solution of radioecological tasks associated with the forecasting the consequences of potential emergencies at nuclear fuel cycle facilities (Alexakhin, 2013; Spiridonov, 2014). All types of accidents accompanied by radioactive releases into the atmosphere lead to non-uniform contamination of the territories with radionuclides. We should emphasise that distributions of radioactive substances deposited on the ground surface due to atmospheric fallout usually follow the lognormal law (Daniels and N.A.Higgins, 2003). For exam-

ple, the results of the analysis of the sets of experimental data on values of surface contamination density (Bq/m^2) of long-lived radionuclides (^{90}Sr , ^{137}Cs , ^{238}Pu , $^{239+240}Pu$, ^{241}Am) for over 60 sites contaminated due to the Chernobyl accident showed that the distribution of only one set is not logarithmically normal (Grubich, 2014; Grubich, 2013). The concentration of radionuclides in non-recultivated soil (Bq/kg) for all databases with large amount of records follows the lognormal statistics without any exceptions.

Results of the statistical processing of the data collected after the Fukushima disaster have also shown the generality of lognormal law for the distribution of the radionuclide activity density (Grubich, 2013). This fact allowed to suggest the law to be applicable in situations associated with the atmospheric deposition of non-radioactive substances as well (Grubich, 2015).

Therefore, application of statistical methods, which consider the probabilistic nature of contamination factor, is logical and reasonable for the assessment and forecast of long-term radioecological consequences of radioactive releases. Statistical assessments in contrast to deterministic approach allow taking into the account the diversity of the most important radioecological indicators (Spiridonov and Ivanov, 2013; Spiridonov and Ivanov, 2014). For instance, the values of the maximum permissible contamination densities of ^{137}Cs for

soils of agricultural lands, which can be used for production meeting the standards (after the Chernobyl accident), can depend heavily on the contamination risks suggested being acceptable (Grubich, 2015).

The present work suggests the further development of a statistical approach to reasonable for the assessment and forecasting the long-term consequences of radioactive contamination of territories using distributed and probabilistic radiation doses for members of the public instead of deterministic and centred dose.

Additional and substantial conditions of the assignment and solution of the task mentioned above are not only the analysis of the mechanism, which characterises the distribution of the set of radionuclides on the contaminated territory but also their consideration in the mutual correlation. The indicators of the mutual correlation, for example, in the form of the covariance matrix, allow the statistical justification of the outputs of application studies devoted to defining the causal relations between the source of the radioactive release and territory contamination.

In such a way strong correlation can indicate a single release (from a single source), and weak correlation can give evidence of repeated releases or releases from various independent sources. The output of such an analysis is supposed to be a distribution of the committed radiation dose for the population for the set of non-independent radionuclides and a calculation of so-called '**probability of excessive population dose**' (PEPD). The excessive dose in PEPD is that part of non-uniformly distributed radiation dose, which exceeds some preassigned value.

The scopes of the work presented in this paper are:

- the development of a statistical approach to the assessment of radiation dose for the population formed by the set of long-lived radionuclides considering their local correlation within the deposition area;
- the formulation of the computational procedure for the calculation of combined multidimensional distribution function depending on partial radiation doses caused by the set of radionuclides contaminating the considered territory and based on the covariance matrix; and, qualitative assessment of the influence of correlations on the probability of excessive population dose.

Materials and methodology

A deterministic approach to the assessment of radiation doses

The conventional method of calculation of radiation dose for the population residing on the contaminated territories is based on the application of dose coefficients (IAEA, 2011; IAEA, 2001). The situations discussed below are assigned with the long-term period

after single depositions varying in radionuclides' content and activities. If the assessment of radiation effects on population does not consider the irradiation from radioactive cloud and inhalation, the main pathways of radiation dose formation will be:

- external exposure to radionuclides contained in the upper soil layer;
- internal exposure to radioactive substances via ingestion.

It is assumed that the population is constantly residing on the radioactively contaminated territory, where they produce only plant foods. Herewith, it is assumed that all contaminated products are consumed by the population for food. According to the assumptions above the radiation dose from external exposure ($D_{ext}^i, Sv/a$) formed by radionuclide i is calculated by the following equation:

$$D_{ext}^i = DC_{ext}^i A^i \quad (1)$$

where DC_{ext}^i is the dose coefficient, $(Sv m^2)/(Bq a)$; A^i is the average soil contamination density of i radionuclide, Bq/m^2 .

The radiation dose from internal exposure ($DC_{int}^i, Sv/a$) formed by radionuclide i is calculated with the formula:

$$D_{int}^i = DC_{int}^i A^i \sum_j TF_i^j V_j P_j \quad (2)$$

where DC_{int}^i is the dose coefficient, Sv/Bq , TF_i^j is the transfer factor for radionuclide i into plant product j , $(Bq/kg)/(Bq/m^2)$, V_j is the consumption rate of j product, kg/a , P_j is the coefficient considering the radionuclide losses while products' processing.

Total partial radiation dose D_i from radionuclide i is equal to the sum of radiation doses from external and internal exposure:

$$D^i = D_{ext}^i + D_{int}^i \quad (3)$$

Total radiation dose for the population constantly living on the contaminated territory and consuming products containing radionuclides is equal to the sum of partial doses:

$$D = \sum_i D^i \quad (4)$$

According to the traditional (deterministic) approach the classification of radioactively contaminated territories is based on the comparison of assessed radiation dose D with the dose standard. Contaminated territories are suggested to be safe when the average value of the radiation dose does not exceed the statutory standard ($1mSv/a$). In case of such ranging there is no any opportunity to estimate the probability of the dose exceeding the standard, which could allow the quantitative assessment of possible ecological hazard.

Additionally, the deterministic approach, which operates with the monitoring data in the form of average values and is applicable for the assessment of the

hazards from radioactively contaminated territories, ignores the contribution of mutual correlations of pollutants. This results in the lack of analysis outputs and uncertainty of the forecasting the existing radioecological situation.

Information about the interdependency of contaminants in the form of covariance matrix could significantly complement the monitoring results. It also could be used both for detailed investigations of environmental hazards and for defining the history and release sources, which led to the territory contamination. The procedure of obtaining the covariance matrix components from the collected monitoring data is provided in Annex 1 to the current paper.

The probability of excessive population dose

Within the statistical approach proposed earlier (Spiridonov and Ivanov, 2013; Spiridonov and Ivanov, 2014), one of the informative probabilistic characteristics associated with the distributed radiation dose can be the probability of the dose, which exceeds any preassigned value.

According to the definition, the probability of excessive population dose R is equal to the probability of the random value of the radiation dose ξ exceeding some other value λ , which is further called **standard**:

$$R = P(\xi > \lambda) = 1 - P(\xi \leq \lambda) \quad (5)$$

where $P(\xi \leq \lambda)$ is the distribution function.

In the simplest case, when the value ξ is distributed according to the normal law, the value of PEPD for the standard λ depends on the expected value of the dose distribution μ and variance σ^2

$$R = [1 - \text{erf}(\frac{\lambda - \mu}{\sigma\sqrt{2}})]/2 \quad (6)$$

where $\text{erf}(x)$ – error function integral.

It is obvious that if the standard λ is equal to the average value μ , then the value of PEPD will be equal to 0.5, in case of $\lambda = \mu + \sigma$ the PEPD value will be 0.17, and for $\lambda = \mu + 2\sigma$ PEPD value will be less than 0.03.

Contamination by correlated normally distributed sources

Statistic model, which allows receiving the distribution functions of radiation doses on contaminated territories, is formed in the following way. Let us assume that radiation dose on the contaminated territory is formed by partial contributions from several various radionuclides, i.e. the random value of total dose ξ is equal to the sum of random doses ξ_i from each radionuclide:

$$\xi = \sum_i \xi_i \quad (7)$$

It is known that amount of normally distributed random values of ξ_i forms the random value of ξ , which distribution will also follow the normal law. Moreover, if the mean of radiation dose from each i radionuclide is $\mu_i = \langle \xi_i \rangle$ then the expected value of the total dose μ will be equal to the sum of average partial doses:

$$\mu = \langle \xi \rangle = \sum_i \mu_i \quad (8)$$

For dependent components of the contamination, radiation dose from which is distributed according to the normal law $N(\mu_i, \sigma_i)$ the variance σ^2 contains additional members bound with the non-zero off-diagonal part of covariance matrix:

$$\sigma^2 = \sum_{i,j} \sigma_{ij} \quad (9)$$

where $\sigma_{ij} = \langle (\xi_i - \mu_i)(\xi_j - \mu_j) \rangle = \langle \xi_i \xi_j \rangle - \mu_i \mu_j$. In case of a mutually independent contribution, off-diagonal members of the covariance matrix are equal to zero.

Non-zero off-diagonal additives to being significant can lead to the essential variations of PEPD value (5) in comparison with the case of independent contamination components. This situation is presented below.

Computer modelling of the radiation doses formed by the set of normally distributed radionuclides should be based on the multidimensional probability density. In this work, we used the original covariance matrix σ_{ij} for generalisation of the random data selection responding to the combined distribution. Specially designed program code uses the Cholesky decomposition, which leads the matrix σ_{ij} to the special triangle view. Modelling details for correlated random values of radiation doses from each radionuclide as well as the code of the corresponding program are the separate topic and are not discussed in the current paper.

Contamination by correlated log-normally distributed sources

Radioecological monitoring data usually point at asymmetrical law of the distribution of contamination densities and doses from various radionuclides, which differs from the normal distribution. Moreover, the last investigation data denote the universal character of distributions of activity densities of ^{90}Sr , ^{137}Cs , ^{238}Pu , $^{239+240}\text{Pu}$, ^{241}Am and activity concentrations in soil, which correspond to log-normal distribution (Grubich, 2013).

The developed program code allows realising the random data selection from the multidimensional function of the distribution of radiation dose defined by a set of radionuclides distributed according to the log-normal law. In contrast to the case considered before, linear combination ξ_i of lognormally distributed random values forms the random value of ξ with unknown

distribution, for which, however, the average value of total dose μ is equal to the sum of average doses, as above (8).

Variance of total radiation dose σ^2 has additional members, as above. These members are attributed to non-zero non-diagonal part of covariance matrix but related to correlating lognormally distributed values of radiation dose (9). Modelling of random values, given as combined lognormal distribution, is a separate interdisciplinary mathematical task, numerical solution of which is used in series of applied studies (Guiahi, 2007; Wu, 2005; Thomopoulos and Johnson, 2004; Law and Kelton, 2000; Levy, 2012; Yue, 2002; Li, 2008). Details and important and useful formulas used for this are given in Annex 2 to the article.

The procedure of contamination modelling, preassigned as a sum of random lognormal values of radiation dose from various radionuclides, includes the performing of the following stages:

- basing on the original monitoring statistics (the expected value and the dose variance of preassigned contamination components) and using the above-given formulas we calculate the statistics of conormal distribution of each component;
- then we use the obtained values of statistics of conormal distributions to generate the set of random data selections in the same way as for modelling the distribution, formed by the sum of random normally distributed radiation doses.

After that, random values of the set of conormal components, which are used as the degree of the exponent, allow creating the required random data selection from the combined multidimensional dose distribution formed by the lognormally distributed contamination radionuclides.

Results

On the basis of the developed methodology, we performed computer modelling and test calculations of statistics of radiation dose for multicomponent correlated contamination for the following cases.

Modelling of random dependent normal components. Figures 1 and 2 show the results of test calculation in case of modelling the distributed radiation dose from the stochastic contamination with five different radionuclides, distributed according to the normal law and forming the same average dose $\mu_i = 1$. Due to the illustrating and conventional character of the test calculation, absolute values and measurement units of radiation dose are not significant for the qualitative outputs. For example, we can assume mSv/a as a measurement unit for this indicator.

The calculation suggested the covariance matrix σ_{ij} to have the value 0.5 diagonally, and out of the diagonal, the value would be 0.25. The results of the modelling of the correlated selection of contamination

Figure 1: Densities of the probability of the dose distribution, formed by the set of normally distributed partial doses (independent - blue, correlated - red).

Figure 2: Probability of excessive population dose caused by the set of normally distributed partial doses (independent - blue, correlated - red).

are compared with the model data selection for the same, but independent normal contamination components. The volume of the computer generation of both selections consists of 100,000 random values.

The expected value of radiation dose $\mu = 5$. Variance of the selection of correlated doses $\sigma^2 = 7.5$ significantly exceeds the same for independent contamination components, which is equal 2.5. Taking advantage of the fact that the distribution for the sum of normally distributed values follows the normal law as well, we can obtain *PEPD* from the equation (6).

The estimation of *PEPD* gives the following results: when the standard is equal to average $\lambda = 5$, the values of *PEPD* for both cases (independent and correlated contamination) will be the same and equal to 0.5. In the case of $\lambda = 7$, the value of *PEPD* for correlated contamination will be two times higher - 0.2 instead of 0.1 as for the case of independent contamination.

Modelling of random dependent lognormal components. Figures 3 and 4 show the results of numeric modelling of the distribution of total radiation dose caused by five random doses, distributed according to the lognormal law and having the same average $\mu_i = 1$. The demonstration covariance matrix σ_{ij} to have the value 0.5 diagonally, and out of the diagonal, the value would be 0.25. The results of the modelling of the radiation dose from the correlated selection are

Figure 3: Densities of the probability of the dose distribution, formed by the set of lognormally distributed partial doses (independent - blue, correlated - red).

Figure 4: Probability of excessive population dose caused by the set of normally distributed partial doses (independent - blue, correlated - red).

compared with the radiation dose from the selection of the same but independent lognormal partial doses. The generation volume of both selections consists of 50 000 random values. As in the case of normal distribution (fig. 1) the mean of total radiation dose from the radionuclides $\mu = 5$, and variance is $\sigma^2 = 7.5$, that exceeds the same value in case of independent lognormal doses equal to 2.5.

Discussion

Modelling of the simplest normally distributed multicomponent contamination allows in a quality manner to follow the direct dependence of the change of *PEPD* value on the colligation of contamination components. We should note here, that such distribution is almost never realised in practice, but its modelling is useful in a methodological point of view as a control case.

Value of *PEPD* for the dose exceeding the average λ increases with the growth of positive correlation between doses from separate radionuclides. As the test calculation shows, for example, for $\lambda = 7$ the value of *PEPD* for correlated contamination will be two times higher - 0.2 instead of 0.1 as for the case of independent contamination. Therefore, underestimation of correlation of contamination components can lead

to the significant mistakes in the forecasts of radiation doses from multicomponent contamination.

Modelling of random dependent lognormal contamination components. We should mention here the peculiarities of the obtained numerical results of the modelling of the distribution of total radiation dose from the contributions composed by lognormally distributed doses from separate radionuclides.

First, both distributions (correlated and independent components) are asymmetrical (fig. 3). The peak of the distribution curve is displaced to the left from the position of mean value. Moreover, the value of the skewness increases with the growth of variance σ^2 for correlated radiation doses.

Second, the statistics of μ and σ^2 do not allow the estimation of *PEPD* value as some general equation, similar to (6), because both combined distributions (fig. 3) are not lognormal in general case (Li, 2008). Besides, in case of correlation, the *PEPD* value depends on the off-diagonal members of covariance matrix. For this reason in each particular case we should estimate the *PEPD* by way of separate numerical modelling of the combined multidimensional distribution of radiation dose from the set of contamination components.

Thirdly, *PEPD* for the sum of average partial doses (fig. 4) exceeds the value of 0.5 (50 %), which was obtained in case of normally distributed doses and this distinction grows at the growth of correlation of doses from different radionuclides. In particular, the *PEPD* exceeding, for example, the average value is equal to 58 % for independent and 65 % for dependent partial radiation doses.

The statistical approach, the modelling procedure, methodology and the results of computer modelling allow to estimate and demonstrate the significance of the consideration of correlation of the components of radioactive contamination of the territories in case of the dose assessment for the members of the public. It is worthwhile to say that this aspect is usually missed out at prognostic calculations. At the same time, for the situations connected with the simultaneous release of the set of different radionuclides into the atmosphere (contamination components), the consideration of their correlation allows avoiding the underestimation of the probability of formation of radiation doses for the population exceeding the average values.

The analysis performed in this paper is due to the fact that at the current stage of the radioecological development significant attention is paid to the issues associated with the analysis of the uncertainties of radioecological assessments. For example, the program of strategic studies developed by the leading European radioecological centres (Research, 2012) contains the statements of key directions of intended works, which indicate these issues.

The authors offer a statistical approach to the assessment of distributed radiation doses from correlated sources being the components of non-uniform radioactive contamination. This approach can be used for the

solution of other application tasks. Such tasks include the assessment of the consequences of aerosol contamination of the atmosphere, surface and ground waters, and dose calculations at combined correlated contamination of soils with a set of various toxic agents (heavy metals, pesticides, etc.).

Annex 1

Consideration of correlation of the components of radioactive contamination of the territories. The methodology used for the development of geoinformational databases and maps of radioactive contamination includes the soil sampling on the territories affected by the radioactive fallout. The collected data on the content of different radionuclides in soil samples allow obtaining an averaged contamination density (arithmetic average) and its variability for each particular territory.

At the calculation of the radiation dose from the radionuclide i , we assume that it is a random value with its partial distribution, which parameters correspond to experimentally obtained statistics - mean μ_i and variance σ_i^2 .

When we obtain the statistics from collected field data we hardly ever evaluate the correlations of the dose contributions from different radionuclides, though the values of the covariance matrix can always be calculated using the available information. The simple formulas for calculation of experimental statistics including the values of covariance matrix σ_{ij} are given below.

Let the dose values calculated on the basis of the data selection from n samples to be gathered in the table T_{ki} , where there are the dose values from radionuclide i in the columns and results for sampling point k in the rows. Then averaging over the columns allows to calculate the expected value of dose from the i radionuclide μ_i , its variance σ_i^2 and covariance matrix σ_{ij} from the i and j radionuclides using the following equations:

$$\mu_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_k T_{ki}; \quad \sigma_i^2 = \sigma_{ii}$$

$$\sigma_{ij} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_k (T_{ki} - \mu_i)(T_{kj} - \mu_j)$$

where summation in the equations is performed over n collected samples.

Results of the evaluation of the symmetrical by definition covariance matrix σ_{ij} obtained using the above formulas represent the additional valuable information about the statistical properties of territory contamination, which is usually missed out by the researchers. In particular, zero values of the off-diagonal members of the matrix σ_{ij} allow to define historically independent contamination components and draw the conclusions on the cause-and-effect relations of the contaminations with several independent radioactive releases.

In the general case, which considers the correlation of different radionuclides, the combined distribution function becomes multidimensional (is not breaking apart on the multiplication of one-dimension variables), moreover the expected value of radiation dose μ , which calculation was based on the average contamination density, and its variance σ^2 are expressed with the following way:

$$\mu = \sum_i \mu_i; \quad \sigma^2 = \sum_{ij} \sigma_{ij}$$

where σ_{ij} is the covariance matrix of the distribution function of i and j contamination components, and summation is performed over all the radionuclides.

The diagonal matrix σ_{ij} with zero off-diagonal elements corresponds to the absence of correlations, besides in this particular case of independent contamination components: $\sigma^2 = \sum_i \sigma_i^2$

Annex 2

Let the random variable y be distributed according to the normal law $N(\mu_y, \sigma_y)$, where μ_y is its mean, and σ_y is its standard deviation. If the other variable x is associated with y in a way $y = \lg(x)$, then x follows the lognormal distribution $LN(\mu_x, \sigma_x)$. The expected value μ_x and standard deviation σ_x of the latter are bound with the statistics of the normal distribution, which further is called companion or conormal, by the following formulas:

$$\mu_x = \exp\left(\mu_y + \frac{\sigma_y^2}{2}\right)$$

$$\sigma_x^2 = \mu_x^2(\exp(\sigma_y^2) - 1)$$

Statistics of conormal distribution $N(\mu_y, \sigma_y)$ for their part are expressed through the mean μ_x and standard deviation σ_x of the lognormal distribution in the form:

$$\mu_y = \lg(\mu_x) - \frac{1}{2} \lg\left(1 + \frac{\sigma_x^2}{\mu_x^2}\right)$$

$$\sigma_y^2 = \lg\left(1 + \frac{\sigma_x^2}{\mu_x^2}\right)$$

The relations expressing the elements of the latter matrix through the components of the covariance matrix $\sigma_{x_i x_j}$ are useful for the software implementation of the combined distribution of several correlated among each other lognormal random variables y_i associated by the covariance matrix $\sigma_{y_i y_j}$:

$$\sigma_{y_i y_j} = \lg\left(1 + \frac{\sigma_{x_i x_j}}{|\mu_{x_i} \mu_{x_j}|}\right)$$

$$\sigma_{x_i x_j} = \mu_{x_i} \mu_{x_j} [\exp(\sigma_{y_i y_j}) - 1]$$

where $|\mu_{x_i} \mu_{x_j}|$ is the absolute value of the product of expected values of conormal random variables x_i and x_j .

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